

Adsorption of Cetyl-trimethyl Ammonium Bromide (CTAB) on Liquid-Paraffin-Water Interface

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The adsorption of cetyl trimethyl ammonium bromide at different concentrations on liquid paraffin/water interface has been measured by the interfacial tension lowering method and also by the emulsion technique at 30°C. The results obtained by the two methods agree within the limits of experimental error.

The experimental data on adsorption appear to fit both the Freundlich and Langmuir adsorption isotherms.

The adsorption of cetyl-trimethyl ammonium ion on oil/water interface has been investigated by a number of authors¹⁻⁵ using the method of lowering of interfacial tension combined with Gibbs equation. As measurement of adsorption by more than one method is very desirable we undertook the study of adsorption of CTAB at liquid paraffin water interface by two independent methods. One of them is based on the measurement of lowering of interfacial tension (γ) combined with Gibb's equation and the other is based on direct estimation of CTAB by titration technique before and after dispersion of a given volume of liquid paraffin in a known volume of CTAB solution of constant ionic strength.

From the first method we get the number of gm-ions adsorbed per 1 cm² of the interface using Gibb's isotherm $\Gamma = -\frac{1}{2.303 RT} \cdot \frac{dy}{d \log C}$. The use of Gibb's isotherm in this form is justified as in our experiments there has always been present a sufficient excess of added neutral electrolyte⁶⁻⁸. The second method is based on the direct estimation of adsorption on the oil globules (formed by dispersing a definite volume of oil in a given volume of CTAB solution of known concentration) by titration in chloroform medium with an ionic surfactant, viz., sodium dodecyl sulphate solution using bromophenol blue as an indicator. From the difference in concentration of the CTAB solution before and after dispersion of the oil, the adsorption on the total surface of the globules is calculated. It may be assumed that the total surface area of the oil globules remains constant when the volumes of the oil and the CTAB solutions are maintained constant and the dispersion is effected in exactly the same way, while the conⁿ of the CTAB only in the solutions is varied within certain limits. The data on adsorption thus obtained may be used to test the various adsorption isotherms.

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EXPERIMENTAL

The stabiliser CTAB, $\text{CH}_3(\text{CH}_2)_{15}(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{N}^+\text{Br}^-$ mol. wt. 364.45, is the product of BDH Ltd., Poole, England. It is purified by repeated recrystallisation from hot alcohol and the purified sample is analysed by the micromethod for its content of C, H and N. These are found to be 6.2, 11.8 and 3.8 percent respectively.

The analysis of the sample thus confirms its purity. Moreover its c.m.c. in aqueous solution has been determined by surface tension as well as by conductivity measurements. It has been found to be 0.00087. The approximate value of c.m.c. of the C_{16} -amine salt quoted in the literature is 0.00089. The characteristic minimum in the surface tension vs concentration curve due to presence of impurity has not been observed (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1.

Liquid paraffin of B.P. quality has been used for our investigation without further purification. Double distilled water of sp. conductivity = $0.57 \times 10^{-6} \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ has been used throughout the experiment.

Ionic strength at 0.01 has been maintained by Analar hydrochloric acid only while that at 0.02 has been maintained by hydrochloric acid as well as by pure sodium chloride in 1 : 1 ratio.

Measurement of interfacial tension (γ) at liq-paraffin-water interface.

We have measured interfacial tension (γ) of this system using Du Nouÿ tensiometer.

TABLE I

Conc. of CTAB gm-mole/l $C \times 10^4$	Adsorbed amount gm-ion/cm ² $\Gamma \times 10^{10}$	Adsorbed amount gm-ion/cm ² $\Gamma \times 10^{10}$
	From Gibb's eq ⁿ at ionic strength=0.01 at 30°C.	
	From Gibb's eq ⁿ at ionic strength=0.02 at 30°C.	
3.01	3.80	4.18
2.41	3.48	4.18
2.11	3.18	3.83
1.81	2.96	3.57
1.50	2.61	3.13
1.20	2.18	2.70
0.90	1.74	2.39
0.66	1.39	2.00

The instrument has been calibrated by using pure liquids of known surface tension at a constant room temperature. The adsorbed amount per 1 cm² of the interface, Γ , has been calculated from the Gibb's isotherm knowing the value of $dr/d\log c$ from a graphical plot of γ against $\log C$. The data are recorded in Table I.

Measurement of total adsorption on the emulsion globules.

A given volume of the CTAB solution of known concentration has been shaken with a given volume of liquid paraffin in a stoppered glass bottle containing glass beads and avoiding air as far as possible. The resulting emulsions has then been homogenized in a hand operated homogenizer. All the emulsions have been prepared in the same way. These emulsions have then been allowed to stand until the aqueous phase near the bottom of the bottle has become clear. A portion of the clear solution has been withdrawn carefully with a syringe having a long needle. The concentration of the CTAB has then been determined by titration in chloroform medium with sodium dodecyl sulphate solution using bromophenol blue as an indicator. From the difference in concentration of the CTAB in the aqueous phase before and after emulsification, the amount adsorbed has been calculated. The data are recorded in Tables II and III.

TABLE II

Ionic strength=0.01 ; Temperature=30°C.

Conc ⁿ of CTAB in the aqueous phase before dispersion in gm-mole/l C × 10 ⁴	Conc ⁿ of CTAB in the aqueous phase after dispersion in gm-mole/l C × 10 ⁴	Adsorbed amount in gm-ion/10 ml. of liq-paraffin. X × 10 ⁶
2.92	1.88	10.4
2.75	1.75	10.0
2.24	1.36	8.8
1.92	1.12	8.0
1.62	0.90	7.2

TABLE III

Ionic strength=0.02 ; Temperature=30°C.

Conc ⁿ of CTAB in the aqueous phase before dispersion in gm-mole/l C × 10 ⁴	Conc ⁿ of CTAB in the aqueous phase after dispersion in gm-mole/l C × 10 ⁴	Adsorbed amount in gm-ion/10 ml. of liquid paraffin X × 10 ⁶
2.99	1.83	11.6
2.64	1.58	10.6
2.29	1.28	10.1
1.94	1.06	8.8
1.58	0.82	7.6

TABLE IV

Ionic strength=0.01

Adsorption in gm-ion/10 ml. of liquid paraffin $x \times 10^6$	Adsorption in gm-ion/cm ² $\Gamma \times 10^{10}$ From Gibb's eq ⁿ at ionic strength=0.01 at 30°C.	Total surface area (S) in cm ² $\frac{(S=x) \times 10^{-4}}{\Gamma}$
10.4	2.90	3.586
10.4	2.82	3.546
8.8	2.40	3.667
8.0	2.26	3.540
7.2	1.74	—

Average value of $S=3.585=10^4 \text{ cm}^2$

TABLE V

Ionic strength = 0.02

Adsorption in gm-ion / 10 ml. of liquid paraffin $x \times 10^6$	Adsorption in gm-ion/cm ² $\Gamma \times 10^{10}$ From Gbbs eqn at ionic Strength =0.01 at 30°C.	Total surface area (S) in cm ² $\frac{(S=x) \times 10^4}{\Gamma}$
11.6	3.60	3.355
10.6	3.26	3.256
10.1	2.90	3.482
8.8	2.60	3.385
7.6	1.94	—

Average value of $S=3.370 \times 10^4 \text{ cm}^2$

DISCUSSION

The applicability of Freundlich¹⁰ and Langmuir¹¹ isotherms to the adsorption of cetyl-trimethyl ammonium bromide ion at liq-paraffin-water interface has been tested

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with the data recorded in Tables II and III. A plot of $\log x$ against $\log C$ yields a straight line (Fig. 3 (a,b) for each of the ionic strengths investigated. Therefore, it may be concluded that Freundlich isotherm holds for the adsorption of CTAB at this interface.

Vold and Groot¹² and later on Ghosh¹³ have shown that Langmuir isotherm can be tested by plotting $1/x$ against $1/Cf$ where f is the mean activity coefficient. A plot of $1/x$ against $1/Cf$ yields a straight line Fig. 2(a,b) for each of the ionic strengths investigated. We may, therefore, conclude that Langmuir isotherm also holds good for this interface over the range of concentrations of CTAB investigated.

Fig 3

The actual adsorption (x) on the oil globules is directly proportional to the adsorption per cm^2 of the interface, Γ , found from Gibb's equation i.e., $x \propto \Gamma$. The proportionality constant, here, is obviously the total surface area S , i.e., $x = S\Gamma$ or $S = x/\Gamma$ cm^2 , S , has been calculated in this way by combining the two methods for measuring the adsorption. The data are recorded in Tables IV and V. It appears from these data that S is fairly constant over the range of concentrations of CTAB investigated. The fact that $\Gamma \propto (x)$ indicates that the two methods used for measurement of adsorption lead to concordant results.

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